

FRAMEWORK FOR OUTLIER DETECTION IN LARGE-SCALE DATASETS USING LOCAL DYNAMIC NEIGHBORHOODS

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ABSTRACT:

Local outlier detection is a hot area and great challenge in data mining, especially for large-scale datasets. On the one hand, traditional algorithms often achieve low-quality detection results and are sensitive to neighborhood size. On the other hand, they are infeasible for large-scale datasets due to at least $O(N^2)$ time and space complexity. In light of these, we propose a new local outlier detection algorithm, which is designed based on a new stable neighborhood strategy-dynamic references nearest neighbors (DRNN). Meanwhile, we present a new detection framework by combining the proposed approach and k-mean for large-scale datasets. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed algorithm can produce higher quality and robust detection results compared to several classic methods. Meanwhile, the new detection framework is able to significantly improve detecting efficiency without sacrificing accuracy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on basic definitions of an outlier [1,2], local outlier detection aims to capture the records that are deviant from their neighbors. Compare to global outliers, local outliers are more interesting and challenge in data mining and machine learning. At

present, several strategies [3–7] have been proposed for outlier detection and many algorithms have been developed for various practical applications [8–13]. Particularly, local outlier detection includes two basic tasks: how to quantify neighborhood of a data object and how to estimate local outlier degree of a data object. In general, most local algorithms use k-nearest neighbors (kNN) to measure their neighborhoods and define their outlier factor according to different strategies, such as distance and density.

However, traditional local algorithms usually obtain lowquality results and are sensitive to neighborhood parameter, such as parameter k. Most traditional algorithms use kNN to quantify their neighborhood of data objects. As is well known, kNN quantifies a rounded or spherical local region, therefore, it is a rough neighborhood measurement and not feasible for datasets with non-spherical clusters. Moreover, it is hard to set k value without prior knowledge and the kNN-based detection algorithms are usually sensitive to k due to instability of kNN. Thus, many convenient local approaches often show poor detection performance and low robustness, especially for datasets with complex distributions.

Furthermore, nearest neighbors based algorithms generally take $O(N^2)$ time and

$O(N^2 D)$ space complexity to construct the affinity matrix, where N and d are the data size and the dimension, respectively. As the data size N increases, the computational and storage burden of them grows dramatically. For example, given a dataset with 1 million samples, the $N \times N$ affinity matrix will need 7,450.58 GB of memory, which could lead to the memory bottleneck of a common computer, not to mention the next phase of detection process.

To alleviate the problems mentioned above, a novel Local Dynamic Neighborhood based Detection algorithm (LDNOD for short) which includes new definitions of neighborhood and outlier degree has been proposed. To measure a stable and accurate neighborhood for arbitrary data, a new nearest neighbors measurement, named Dynamic References Nearest Neighbors (DRNN) that searches neighbors based on dynamic references instead of a fixed and single reference, is designed first. Based on DRNN, a new outlier factor is defined to score each region rather than each data object. Toward large-scale data, a detection framework (LDNOD-km) by combining advantages of LDNOD and k-means is developed. Extensive experiments have been conducted on various datasets, which have shown the advantages of the LDNOD and LDNOD-km compared with several the-state-of-art algorithms.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Identification of outliers

The problem of outliers is one of the oldest in statistics, and during the last century and a half interest in it has waxed and waned several times. Currently it is once again an

active research area after some years of relative neglect, and recent work has solved a number of old problems in outlier theory, and identified new ones. The major results are, however, scattered amongst many journal articles, and for some time there has been a clear need to bring them together in one place. That was the original intention of this monograph.

A survey of outlier detection methodologies

Outlier detection has been used for centuries to detect and, where appropriate, remove anomalous observations from data. Outliers arise due to mechanical faults, changes in system behaviour, fraudulent behaviour, human error, instrument error or simply through natural deviations in populations. Their detection can identify system faults and fraud before they escalate with potentially catastrophic consequences. It can identify errors and remove their contaminating effect on the data set and as such to purify the data for processing

3. EXISTING SYSTEM:

Based on basic definitions of an outlier local outlier detection aims to capture the records that are deviant from their neighbors. Compare to global outliers, local outliers are more interesting and challenge in data mining and machine learning.

Disadvantages:

- Less accuracy

4. PROPOSAL SYSTEM:

In data mining, particularly for large-scale datasets, local outlier detection is a popular

topic and a significant difficulty. Traditional algorithms are sensitive to neighborhood size and frequently produce poor detection results, on the one hand. However, due to at least $O(N^2)$, they are impractical for huge datasets. Complexity in time and space. As a result, we provide a new local outlier detection approach that is built using a new, dynamic neighborhood strategy that refers to the closest neighbours (DRNN). The proposed technique and k-mean are combined in a novel detection framework that we present in the interim. enormous datasets. The proposed method can produce improved quality outcomes, according to experimental findings. quality and reliable detection outcomes in comparison to a few conventional techniques. The new detection, however, without compromising accuracy, the framework can considerably increase detection efficiency.

Advantages:

High accuracy

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

6. IMPLEMENTATION

User:

user information and task descriptions for the entire experiment. user after uploading datasets propose algorithm will apply KMEANS algorithm to group similar data in clusters and then this clusters will be evaluated with neighbour instances to get similarity score. Sum of similarity score of all instances with the compare has good matching score then that record will be accepted otherwise that record will be consider as outlier and removed out from dataset.

To implement this project we have used KDD dataset and then train Random Forest algorithm with and without outlier detection and then compare their accuracy and other metrics.

To implement this project we have designed following modules

1) Upload KDD Dataset: using this module we will upload dataset to application

2) Preprocess Dataset: dataset often contains missing values and non-numeric characters data so by using this values we will replace missing values with 0 and then encode all non-numeric data to numeric id.

3) Run Random Forest on Full Dataset: using this module we will train Random Forest algorithm on full dataset without outlier detection and then calculate its accuracy

4) Run K-Means Algorithm: using this module we will cluster entire dataset into different groups

5) LDNOD Outlier Detection with Random Forest: using this module we will read each record from cluster and then calculate its similarity score with its

neighborhood records and if similarity score is high then we will select that record otherwise that record will be consider as outlier. After outlier detection we will retrain data with Random Forest and calculate its accuracy and compare with the one without applying outlier.

6) Comparison Graph: using this module we will plot comparison graph between with and without outlier detection.

Machine learning:

Machine learning refers to the computer's acquisition of a kind of ability to make predictive judgments and make the best decisions by analyzing and learning a large number of existing data. The representation algorithms include deep learning, artificial neural networks, decision trees, enhancement algorithms and so on. The key way for computers to acquire artificial intelligence is machine learning. Nowadays, machine learning plays an important role in various fields of artificial intelligence. Whether in aspects of internet search, biometric identification, auto driving, Mars robot, or in American presidential election, military decision assistants and so on, basically, as long as there is a need for data analysis, machine learning can be used to play a role.

7. CONCLUSION

In this project, a new local detection algorithm (LDNOD) and its framework (LDNOD-km) have been proposed. The LDNOD is insensitive to neighborhood parameter due to the stability of DRNN, which constructs neighborhood of an instance based on dynamic reference objects. Moreover, sharing neighborhoods of close objects and scoring each local region

are designed, which can potentially reduce the running time of LDNOD. Because the LDNOD-km combines the benefits of both LDNOD and k-means, it is able to handle large-scale datasets efficiently without sacrificing accuracy. Finally, experimental results have demonstrated the effectiveness of LDNOD and its framework. In the future, we will further improve LDNOD-km and apply it to handle larger scale and high dimensional datasets.

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